

INDUSTRIAL AREAS LOCATED IN UZBEKISTAN.

Azimova Asaloy Shavkatjon daughter

Teacher of the Department “Applied Mathematics and informatics” of the
Institute of Economics and construction of Andijan

azimova.asaloy@mail.ru

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Abstract: This article covers the industrial areas located in the Republic of Uzbekistan and introducing development processes into practice to this day, which are constantly increasing the production cost of practical support for innovative projects.

Key words: Snt, industri, power plant, factory, factory, capitalist, staircase, corporate.

Industry is said to be a complex that produces raw materials, materials, fuels, energy and other products or serves the population. Industry is a branch of the national economy.

Industrial industry—a leading branch of the national economy, which has a decisive influence on the level of development of the productive forces of society; a set of enterprises (factories, factories, power plants, mines, mines, etc.) occupied by the production of Labor weapons and other products for the industry itself and for other sectors of the national economy, as well as the production of The industry forms the basis of expanded reproduction and provides industrial growth. According to the classification adopted in the 80s of the 20th century, the industry is divided into 18 industries, which are enlarged: electroenergetics; fuel industry; ferrous metallurgy; non-ferrous metallurgy; chemical and petrochemical industry; mechanical engineering and metalworking; forest, woodworking and pulp industry; building materials industry; construction extractions and details industry; window and chinnifayans industry; Light S; food industry; microbiology industry; unyorma and mixed feed industry; medical industry; polygraph industries are also grouped in turn - into types of processing industry and incendiary industries.

The emergence of industry as an independent branch of social production is associated with the separation of crafts from agriculture — the second largest division of Labor. Capitalist industry appeared in the countries of Western Europe in the 14th-15th centuries and went through the stages of ordinary capitalist cooperation, Manufactory and large mashipa industry — factory, the transition from Manufactory to the mashipa industry at the beginning of the 18th ASG took on the tone of an industrial coup, initially in England, and later in

other European countries. In Russia and other augim countries, the industry has evolved from the beginning of the 18th asg in the form of Manufactory, from the 2nd half of the 19th asgpipd, the mashipa industry has evolved.

The root of industrial development in the territory of Uzbekistan was the creation of crafts with a long history. Small and large crafts developed in cities such as Samarkand, Vihogo, Urgench, Tashkent, Kokand, Margilan, Namangan, Andijan. The emergence of a truly meaningful industry in Uzbekistan.

It dates back to the 2nd half of the 19th century. As a result of the occupation of Central Asia by Tsarist Russia, Russian industrialists and Russian capital also entered the country, and industries with primary processing of raw materials (cotton cleaning, wine, vodka, Canning, cotton oil factories) appeared, and industry in Uzbekistan developed in connection with Russian industry and economy. In 1913, in the production of gross products on the territory of Uzbekistan, the contribution of heavy industry was 2%, Metal Performance was 1%, light industry was 0.8%, food industry was 14%. Over the next 100 years, the industry of Uzbekistan has formed electroenergetics, gas, oil, silver, ferrous and non-ferrous metallurgy, agricultural machinery (tractors, cotton-picking machines), automotive, cable, electronics, cotton-cleaning industry machinery, Aircraft Engineering, Irrigation-construction machinery, chemical, cement, building materials, medicine, oilmoy, textile, sewing, food and other industries.

20y of the 20th century.from the beginning, industry in Uzbekistan began to develop on the basis of the restoration of small, kustar enterprises, which were in crisis as a result of the World War and the Civil War. Cotton cleaning plants, stairwells, spinning weaves, tailoring, shoe factories began to be built. In 1937, The Tashkent textile combine was launched, 40-50y of the 20th century.from the idol industry, the gas industry, the oil industry began to develop rapidly. During the war of 1941-1945, 90 industrial enterprises were transplanted to Uzbekistan, the kupi of which were mechanical engineering, instrument-making enterprises. In the post-war years, as a result of the construction of many enterprises, machine-building industries increased, aircraft building, instrumentation, motor industry, electro-apparatus, electric motor, excavator, compressor plants were built. Tashkent, Almalyk, Chirchik, Samarkand, Navoi, Fergana, Yangiyul, Namangan, Shursuv and other cities became the center of the chemical industry. Bekabad, Chirchik, ferrous metallurgy in Tashkent, Navoi, Zarafshan, Almalyk, Uchkuduk etc.lari are considered centers of non-ferrous metallurgy.

After Uzbekistan achieved State independence, radical reforms were carried out in the industry, many industrial enterprises in the industry were removed from the state and privatized, transformed into state-owned, corporate, collective, private and other forms of organizational property. Structural restructuring was carried out in industrial networks, which is an important place in the economy of the Republic, many small and medium-sized enterprises were created (in 2000 6.4 thousand medium-sized enterprises, 20.4 thousand small-scale enterprises worked). In cooperation with foreign capital, joint ventures have been established in many industrial networks (see attracting foreign investment in industries, especially in industries that process local raw materials, continues to be active. The role of sectarians in the Republican industry is different. Among industrial networks, industries that process agricultural products and serve the agro-industrial complex have a historically leading position. These are cotton cleaning, silk weaving, Canning, oilmoy and other industrial industries. The chemical and petrochemical, mechanical engineering, electronics, energy, metallurgy, light and building materials industries are developing at a rapid pace. The role of the fuel energy complex in industrial development is special. It includes gas, kumir, oil and oil refining industries, energy. Uzbekistan is included in the sentence of 10 major gas producing countries in the world.

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industrial development is special. It includes gas, kumir, oil and oil refining industries, energy. Uzbekistan is included in the sentence of 10 major gas producing countries in the world. Radical reforms aimed at changing the forms of ownership and making structural changes in industrial networks in Uzbekistan ensure the strengthening of the country's independence, the entry of Uzbekistan into the ranks of developed countries in the future and its integration into the world community. In 2002, Uzbekistan employed 1,467 medium and large production associations and enterprises in the industry. The weight of products produced at these enterprises was 88.5% of the total production volume. The production of new products with more than 396 titles has been mastered. The number of state-owned enterprises was 4.6% salmogi, and the number of non-state-owned industrial enterprises was 95.4%. 20.5% of industrial production employees were employed in state enterprises, 79.5% in non-state enterprises. In the total volume of industrial production, the contribution of state-owned enterprises was 28.6%, and the contribution of non-state-owned enterprises was 71.4% (again, to separate articles on industrial industries such as the automobile industry, Oilmoy industry, machinery industry, etc.).). The development of industry abroad led to the emergence of industrially developed countries. The development of the economy in these countries is based on technologically advanced capital accumulated in large volumes and is ensured by the available highly qualified labor force. They include the USA, Canada, Japan, many Western European countries. Regions with the most industrial enterprises. As of November 1, 2022, the number of operating industrial enterprises (without farms and peasant farms) was 97,054, and this figure increased by 3.3% compared to the corresponding period of 2021. According to the State Statistics Committee, the city of Tashkent is leading in terms of the number of industrial enterprises operating in the region – 16,598. The next places were taken by Fergana region and Andijan region, where 10,785 and 9,799 industrial enterprises operate, respectively. This indicator looked as follows in the section of the remaining regions:

1. Tashkent kegiun-9 795 units;
2. Samarkand kegiun-8 680 units;
3. Namangan kegiun-7 720 units;
4. Kashkadarya kegiun-5 427 units;
5. Bukhara kegiun-4 970 units;
6. Surkhandarya kegiun-4 779 units;
7. Khorezm kegiun-4 736 units;

8. Jizzakh region-4 019 units;
9. Navoi region-3 971 units;
10. Karakalpakstan R. – 3 508 PCs;
11. Syrdarya region-2 267 units.

In the case of this khudular section of our republic, we see that our raw material base in the big bundan has sufficiently efficient drains to generate more production costs but the problem with personnel is one of the areas where we still need to find a solution that is tormenting us.

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